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Geopolitics and Regional Security: Analyzing the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) on the Blue Nile Basin

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ABSTRACT

The Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD), is a monumental infrastructure project on the Blue Nile. It has emerged as a focal point of geopolitical tension and regional security concerns in the Nile Basin. This paper examines the geopolitical and regional security dynamics that surround this massive project, particularly its implications for Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt. The central question of the study is to see how does the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam reshape power relations and regional security in Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt? It aims to understand how large hydro projects act as both development tools and sources of interstate tension in shared river systems. The research uses a qualitative design based on discourse analysis.

The study finds that water securitization and regional alliances are reshaping sovereignty and cooperation in the Nile Basin. It concludes that while the GERD symbolizes Ethiopia's pursuit of developmental autonomy, its sustainability hinges on trust, shared governance, and regional cooperation.

Keywords: *Geopolitics, Regional Security, Conflict Resolution, Hydro politics, Political Ecology*

INTRODUCTION

The Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD), previously recognised as the Millennium Dam, is a monumental hydroelectric project in Africa, symbolizing Ethiopia's aspirations for economic transformation and energy security (Terrefe, B., 2021). It is located on the Blue Nile River in Ethiopia's Benishangul-Gumuz region, near the border with Sudan (Yihdego, Y., Tesfay, Y., & Gebrehiwot, M., 2021). Construction of the GERD began in April 2011, with an initial plan to be completed within five years and to start the impounding phase by 2017 (Ahmed & Elsanabary, 2015; Getachew, 2018). Today, the dam stands fully completed and operational. With a planned capacity of approximately 6,450 megawatts, the GERD is one of the largest dams globally, expected to significantly boost Ethiopia's domestic power supply and provide surplus

energy for export (Yihdego, Y., Tesfay, Y., & Gebrehiwot, M., 2021). The GERD stands 155 meters tall and stretches almost two kilometres in length (Negm, A., et

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al., 2018). The main dam is designed to reach 175 meters in height, while the auxiliary dam will stand at 45 meters (Pietrangeli, B., Bezzi, R., Rossini, M., Masciotta, P., & D'Alberti, M., 2017). The reservoir will cover an area of 1,874 square kilometres and will have a storage capacity equivalent to 1.3 times the annual discharge of the Blue Nile (Yihdego, Salem & Khalil, 2017). The dam is crucial for Ethiopia's goal of becoming a middle-income country, supporting economic development and energy needs.

The GERD has strategic importance for Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt; all of which rely heavily on the Nile for agriculture, energy, and water resources. While Ethiopia views the dam as essential for its growth, Sudan sees both benefits and risks due to its reliance on the Nile for irrigation and hydropower. Egypt, which depends on the Nile for over 95% of its water resources, fears the impact of the GERD on its water supply, particularly given its growing population and agricultural needs (Khayry, F., 2022).

For Ethiopia, the GERD has strategic significance and is critical for energy requirements and its strategy to transition into a middle-income country. The dam is expected to produce over 6,000 megawatts of power, considerably increasing the economy through both domestic consumption and potential export opportunities (Belay, Y., & Abebe, T. B., 2020). As a country with one of the lowest per capita electricity consumption rates, energy access and security are crucial for economic growth (Damena, G., 2020). Ethiopia has initiated several hydroelectric developments to meet the increasing energy demand and plans to export electricity to nearby nations (Ashebir, Dingeto & Hailu, 2022). This project aims to enhance energy security and drive economic growth by improving food security and shifting from subsistence farming to export-oriented agriculture, which relies on reliable irrigation for crops like tea, coffee, and flowers (Handiso, B. W., 2018). As a midstream country, Sudan sees both benefits and risks from the GERD. Situated amid Ethiopia and Egypt, Sudan relies heavily on the Nile for irrigation and hydropower. The Nile is also crucial for Sudanese agriculture, providing irrigation for crops like sorghum, wheat, and cotton, which are vital for food security in the already conflicted region (Basheer, M., Abdo, R., Eldardiry, M., & Khedr, A., 2025). Sudan also utilizes the Nile for hydropower generation, with projects like the Merowe Dam aimed at increasing electricity production (Abdullah, A. M., Rahman, S., Essex, S., & Benhin, J. K. A., 2020). Egypt relies on the Nile for

over 95% of its renewable water resources and has historically controlled its water usage based on colonial-era agreements (Mahemud, Eshtu & Tekuya, 2021). The Nile is vital for Egyptian agriculture, especially for water-intensive crops like cotton and rice, which require extensive irrigation due to the arid climate (Osman, H. S., A. N., & Ouda, A., 2020). The increasing population further intensifies the water pressure.

However, it has to be noted that the significance of GERD extends beyond the immediate riparian countries, influencing regional stability and growth in the broader Nile River Basin. The river supports linked ecosystem for 20 million people across its basin (*Nile Basin Initiative.*, 2020). As the longest river in the world, it passes through countries like Burundi, Rwanda, Tanzania, Kenya, DRC, Uganda, Ethiopia, Eritrea, Sudan, and Egypt, covering about 10% of Africa (National Geographic Education., 2025, May 8). The Nile's two main tributaries, the White Nile and Blue Nile, converge at Khartoum before flowing into Egypt. The river traverses five distinct climate zones, making it crucial for survival in the arid region, where water is essential for agriculture, urbanization, and industry (Hale, T., 2023, March 13).

The reliance on traditional water-intensive crops like cotton and rice, which account for over 85% of water withdrawal, exacerbates the strain on the region's limited water resources (Ouda, S., Amer, M., & Norbha, A., 2018). This intensifies the complexities in managing the Nile's water, as seen in the political challenges surrounding GERD, where competing demands and limited resources have led to diplomatic tensions, threats of military action, and the need for international mediation.

CORE ISSUES

Ethiopia's accession to the 2010 Cooperative Framework Agreement (CFA), was conceived as a modern legal instrument to promote fairness, equity, and shared responsibility among all Nile Basin countries, allowed riparian states to build dams, effectively nullifying colonial-era treaties that favoured Egypt's historical dominance over the Nile (Mbaku, J. M., & Antonio, E. K., 2025). Egypt and Sudan do not accede to the CFA. Their reservations are centred around provisions that redefine water-sharing principles, particularly the idea of "equitable and reasonable utilization." Historically Egypt is the dominant power in Nile politics and has long relied on the 1929 and 1959 water agreements that granted it a majority share of the

river's flow and veto power over upstream projects. From Cairo's perspective, the CFA threatens these established rights and, by extension, its national water security(Wouters and De Chazournes, 2018).

Sudan initially sided with Egypt but holds a more balanced view, recognizing the GERD's potential benefits like flood control, regulated flow, and electricity imports, while remaining concerned about operational safety and coordination. The countries' differing positions on the CFA show Nile water diplomacy is about sovereignty and identity, not just resources. True progress requires Egypt and Sudan to move from historical entitlement to shared destiny, making water a source of collaboration, not confrontation(Kahsay et al., 2015).

On September 10, 2023, Ethiopia completed the filling of the GERD, intensifying the water dispute with Egypt and Sudan (Yihdego, Y., Tesfay, Y., & Gebrehiwot, M., 2021). Egypt views Ethiopia's actions as a threat to its historical entitlement to the Nile's waters, while Ethiopia advocates for "reasonable and equitable" water usage that benefits all parties without causing significant harm (Sayed El Ahi, E. R., ElTarabishi, M., & Rashad, R., 2023). **Egypt does not agree with or recognize the Cooperative Framework Agreement (CFA)**, nor has it signed or ratified the treaty. Egypt's rejection of the CFA is the central point of the legal and political dispute over the Nile River and the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) (Wouters, P. and De Chazournes, L.B., 2018).

Conversely, Ethiopia dismisses Egypt's historical entitlement, promoting a plan of "reasonable and equitable" utilization without imposing "significant harm" based on mutual gains. As a result, the conflict among Egypt, Ethiopia, and Sudan over the GERD remains unresolved.

The unresolved conflict over the GERD has strained diplomatic relations among Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt; with negotiations frequently stalling due to mistrust and conflicting interests. This situation has heightened geopolitical tensions and the risk of conflict in the Nile Basin region, where the core issues include water allocation, environmental concerns, and political tensions. The dispute over the GERD (Map 1), has become a focal point of potential water wars in the region, threatening regional stability. It also includes water allocation and rights, hydrological and environmental concerns, political and diplomatic tensions, and the risk of water wars.

Map 1: Location of GERD, Ethiopia

Source: Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations

Note-The national boundary layer is created on the Database of Global Administrative Areas (GADM)

The present paper aims to evaluate how the construction and operation of GERD affect the geopolitical dynamics amid the Nile Basin countries, particularly Ethiopia, Egypt, and Sudan. It also explores the non-traditional security threats such as water scarcity, and how these could contribute to broader regional security challenges. The study of GERD is crucial for understanding the complex impacts of large-scale infrastructure projects on regional geopolitics, environmental sustainability, economic development, and social well-being. The significance of GERD extends beyond the immediate riparian countries, influencing regional stability and growth throughout the Nile River Basin.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a qualitative and empirical case study design, integrating both primary and secondary data sources. Primary data are derived from satellite imagery, which is employed for spatial visualization of hydrological patterns associated with the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD). Secondary data include scholarly literature, policy documents, treaties, and media reports, which together provide contextual and interpretive depth. The study examines GERD through historical, political, and environmental lenses. The

research generates an in-depth understanding of the dam's implications for water allocation and rights, as well as its broader geopolitical, conflict, and cooperation dynamics within the Nile Basin.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Abdo and Khirelseid (2020), explores about Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam and how it shapes Sudan's environmental and socio-economic future. Author argues that GERD has the potential to transform Sudan's water security and economic growth and regulate the flow of the Blue Nile solving problem of flood also. Infact GERD also opens the door for Sudan to access lower-cost electricity. Regulated water release from GERD could improve the performance of Sudan's own hydropower dams, such as Roseires and Merowe, making energy production more stable. The reduced silt deposition may have long-term implications for soil fertility and during drought years, differences in operational decisions between Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt could create tensions. Despite these concerns, Sudan's potential gains outweigh the risks but only if all three countries commit to joint technical coordination, transparent data sharing, and cooperative water-management mechanisms.

Abdulla (2024) examines the multifaceted positive contributions of Ethiopian diaspora communities in the nation's diplomatic efforts around the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD), highlighting their essential support in advocacy, financial mobilization, expertise sharing, and public diplomacy. Ethiopian diaspora communities have persistently championed Ethiopia's interests regarding GERD through global advocacy and lobbying initiatives. They mobilized networks in regions such as North America, Europe, the Middle East, and Africa, utilizing mainstream and social media platforms to rally support, refute misrepresentations, and highlight the dam's development rationale. Notably, viral campaigns like #ItsMyDam galvanized both Ethiopian nationals and foreign supporters to promote Ethiopia's stance and counter diplomatic pressure. Diaspora through voluntary donations and targeted fundraising financial engagement has been indispensable for GERD's advancement, such as the purchase of diaspora bonds and members provided millions of dollars toward dam construction and subsequent operational stages. This sustained support not only showcased diaspora commitment but also bolstered Ethiopia's capacity to

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assert sovereign ownership over GERD, reducing external dependency.

Abdulla (2024) argues that diaspora communities have played a pivotal role in Ethiopia's diplomacy concerning GERD, spanning advocacy, resource mobilization, and technical support, and cultural outreach, ultimately facilitating progress in the face of external pressures. Their continued engagement is seen as instrumental in transforming Ethiopia's diplomatic landscape through resilient and collaborative strategies.

Abdulla (2020) examines the socio-economic impacts through the perception of local communities, who are affected by development initiatives like Merowe Dam in Sudan. Author have collected data from residents, government officials, dam implementation authority, NON-Government organisation etc. The analysis of the data shows that local people who are affected by these development initiatives are aware of the positive and negative impacts. Positive impacts are majorly increased food production, irrigation supply and electricity supply etc. negative impacts include resettlement, water shortages and rise in cost of electricity. There is policy implication because of these initiatives which include investments in the new settlement areas with respect to the agricultural economy, maintain a balance between different communities like relocated, upstream, and downstream locations.

Ahmed et al (2015) examines the effect of Great Renaissance dam on stream flow of Nile River, especially on Egypt and Sudan. HEC RAC model has been employed to study the possibility of dam damage. By running this model, it has been found that there are some merits and many drawbacks of this project on flow of Nile River. The major problem with this project is some weakness in the design of the dam.

Ali, Awol (2023) uses the concept of counter hydro hegemony which means action taken by weaker or upstream countries to challenge the dominance of downstream countries to use water of Nile River fairly. Signing of Cooperative Framework Agreement (CFA) has been based on fair and reasonable utilization approaches. Upper riparian states are building large dams and irrigation system like GERD, which weakens the historic dominance of Egypt on Nile river basin. In other words, Nile River is entering a new political era where counter hegemonic actions are breaking the old

myths that Egypt should always control the Nile River and this narrative is coming to an end.

Gashaw (2024) offers a comprehensive examination of how Ethiopia's hydropower expansion since 1991 has reshaped the country's geopolitical standing within the Horn of Africa and the wider Nile Basin. Heightened regional contestations around the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) and Ethiopia's broader developmental aspirations. He situates, hydropower development within Ethiopia's post-1991 political restructuring, emphasizing how successive governments have framed large dams like GERD.

Muluken GEMECHU Worku (2024) study the tension and diplomatic deadlock between Ethiopia and Egypt because of the contradictory narration on GERD. The author employed qualitative research approach to understand the issue in greater detail and findings suggest that over politicization of the issue is dominant and there are huge misconception and mistrust on both side which sometimes lead to confrontation. Different actors like successive government officials, media and scholars have deepened the mistrust on popular narrative based on ultra-nationalism and political rhetoric. So, Author recommends that both countries Egypt and Ethiopia should Cooperate and widen diplomatic efforts to build confidence in GERD

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

For studying the GERD and the water conflict amid Ethiopia, Egypt, and Sudan; the selected theoretical framework is Hydropolitics Theory and Political ecology. The Hydro politics framework focuses on the politics of water resource management, particularly in transboundary river basins (Elhance, A. P., 1997). The theory analyses how the GERD influences political relations, negotiations, and power dynamics among Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt (Beyene, M. Z., Biederman, J., & Eshete, K., 2018). The theory can aid decision-makers in analysing collective risk and mitigating potential negative impacts of water conflicts. Therefore, understanding hydro-politics is crucial for predicting possible water-based conflict scenarios between riparian countries (Al-Muqdad, 2022).

In the case of the Nile Basin, water is not just a natural resource; it is a political resource. Ethiopia's decision to build the GERD represents more than an energy project. It is a declaration of sovereignty and self-reliance. Historically Egypt was the dominant power

on the Nile because of colonial-era treaties. While Sudan has balancing approach for cooperation, safety and equitable flow. Hydropolitics becomes the Lense to analyse how rivers become arenas of negotiation, rivalry, and regional diplomacy, reflecting shifting power relations in Northeast Africa (Lavers, 2024).

Another theoretical framework chosen for the study is Political ecology. It brings attention to the people and the environment and focuses on who benefits from large-scale water infrastructure like the GERD, and who bears the cost? While the dam promises clean energy and economic growth, it also raises questions about ecological balance, displacement, and the livelihoods of downstream communities.

The study by Atkins and Hope (2021) indicates that Bolivia and Brazil focused on how political ecology reveals the local scale's importance in critiquing global hydropower projects. So political ecology also emphasizes on the unequal distribution of power and resources in environmental issues. It examines how power dynamics amongst Ethiopia (upstream) and downstream countries like Sudan and Egypt influence decision-making around GERD. This also challenges sustainability claims and reshapes environments. In fact we can say that political ecology reminds us that the environment is deeply political and the decisions about water, energy, and land use reflect issues of justice, inequality, and representation (Harris, L.M., 2020).

Together, these two theories provide a holistic framework for the study. Both frameworks analyse power relations, study inequalities, and equitable water allocation mechanisms offering a comprehensive understanding of the GERD's social, political, and environmental implications. This approach is crucial for fostering regional cooperation, ensuring water security, and achieving sustainable development in the Nile basin (Harris, L.M., 2020). The above-given theories are apt to analyse how the GERD influences political relations, negotiations, and power dynamics among Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt. They explore issues such as water security, power asymmetry, negotiation diplomacy, and the political and strategic dimensions of water resource management in transboundary river basins, helping to understand the strategies and processes through which countries negotiate water-sharing agreements (Casão, A., 2008). Hydropolitics explains the macro-level power dynamics between nations, while Political Ecology helps us understand the micro-level human and environmental impacts.

DISCUSSIONS

EGYPTIAN HEGEMONY OVER THE NILE BASIN: A HISTORICAL AND CONTEMPORARY ANALYSIS

Egyptian hegemony over the Nile basin has been a defining feature of the region's history. It is mainly because of Egypt's strategic dependence on the Nile, its colonial era legal privileges and decades of political leverage. Egypt's dominance over the Nile's water resources stems from a combination of geographic, historical, and political factors. It has shaped the politics of the region for over a century, but now new states assert their rights and new infrastructures like the GERD emerges the historical dominance is being redefined, which is more equitable water governance across the Nile Basin (Zeitoun, M. and Warner, J., 2006).

The ancient Egyptians recognized the Nile's vital importance for their civilization's survival and developed sophisticated irrigation systems to harness its waters (Butzer, K. W., 1976). This historical dependence on the Nile fostered a sense of ownership and entitlement that has persisted through the centuries (Reynolds, 2024). During the colonial era, Britain recognised Egypt's strategic location and granted it substantial control over the Nile's waters through a series of agreements (Moore, S., 2024). In these colonial-era treaties, majority of water rights were granted to Egypt and Sudan via colonial accords, most notably the 1959 treaty, which further cemented Egypt's dominance by excluding upstream countries like Ethiopia (Muyali, 2024). And it laid the foundation for its continued hegemony in the post-colonial period. Due to historical, political, and economic clout, Egypt enjoys a disproportionately large share of the Nile's waters and shaping the region's political and economic landscape (Beyene, M. Z., Biederman, J., & Eshete, K., 2018). Egypt also controls the Aswan High Dam, which allows it to regulate the river's flow and store vast quantities of water, while Ethiopia and Sudan were left with less irrigation infrastructure (Beyene, M. Z., Biederman, J., & Eshete, K., 2018). This hegemony enabled Egypt to secure its water needs and maintain its agricultural and economic development (Moore, S., 2018).

However, in the 21st century, Egyptian hegemony over the Nile basin faced challenges because of the increasing demand for water resources by the rise of upstream countries. This legacy of hydro-hegemony of Egypt is now being challenged by Ethiopia's GERD which also targets to assert the rights of upstream states and promote equitable water sharing (Ali, 2023). However, the absence of comprehensive agreements and weak enforcement mechanisms, hinder cooperation among Nile basin countries, complicating efforts to address future water needs and climate change impacts. Thus, while Egypt's historical claims remain significant, emerging counter-hegemonic dynamics are reshaping the region's water politics (Muyali2024). These developments have led to tensions and disputes between Egypt and its upstream neighbours.

THE GEOPOLITICS OF THE GRAND ETHIOPIAN RENAISSANCE DAM REGION: A COMPLEX WEB OF INTERESTS

Since the announcement and construction of the GERD, it has emerged as a focal point of geopolitical tensions in the region primarily between Ethiopia and downstream countries like Egypt and Sudan. Ethiopia views the dam as crucial for its economic development and energy security, while Egypt, fears a significant reduction in its water supply resulting in a difficult negotiation process that, because of past accords and divergent national interests, has frequently come to a standstill (Wedajo, 2024). Literature indicates that the GERD symbolises a shift in hydro-political dynamics, challenging Egypt's historical hydro-hegemony and prompting Ethiopia to assert its rights to utilise shared water resources (Ali, 2023). Climate change and population expansion add to the complexity of this scenario by intensifying competition for water supplies, which could spark conflict if cooperative solutions are not given priority. Therefore, fostering a cooperative framework that acknowledges the interests of all parties is crucial for regional stability and sustainable water management (Gashaw, 2024).

COMPETING INTERESTS AND PERSPECTIVES

The construction of GERD has ignited intense nationalist sentiments in both Ethiopia and Egypt and

has become a focal point for historical grievances and contemporary anxieties. The dam is presented as a sign of national pride and economic progress in Ethiopia, while Egyptian media frequently highlights worries about water security and past agreements that support their interests (Wedajo, 2024). Ultimately, GERD serves as an example of how national identity and geopolitical concerns may entangle infrastructure projects, requiring cooperative solutions to prevent future problems.

In Ethiopia, the GERD represents national pride, nation self-reliance, and a pathway to economic transformation. The dam is expected to generate a significant amount of electricity, addressing Ethiopia's chronic energy shortages and boosting its industrial development, thereby enhancing economic landscape (Wedajo, 2024). The dam is also a means to assert its sovereignty over the Nile's waters and challenge the historical dominance of Egypt and fostering a narrative of reclamation of water rights (Quagliarotti, 2023). The government has actively promoted the GERD as a national project, emphasising its potential to generate electricity, boost industrial development, and alleviate poverty.

This narrative has resonated deeply with the Ethiopian public, who see the GERD as a source of national pride and a testament to Ethiopia's resilience, determination, and reinforcing national identity. It has become a rallying point uniting Ethiopians across ethnic and political divides (Quagliarotti, 2023). However, the GERD has sparked tensions with Egypt and Sudan, who fear negative effects on their water rights, leading to a protracted negotiation process that has often ended in stalemate (Goldberg, 2023).

Conversely, Egypt has viewed the GERD as an existential threat to its water security and national interests, as the Nile is the lifeblood of Egypt. Egypt's initial response to the GERD was marked by strong opposition and even veiled threats of military action (Gomaa, M. E., 2018). And any perceived reduction in its flow is seen as a direct challenge to the country's survival. It fears that the dam's filling and operation could reduce the flow of the Nile, impacting its agriculture, industry, and overall water

security (Gomaa, M. E., 2018). This rhetoric fuelled concerns about a potential conflict in the Nile Basin, raising the stakes for all involved. And hence the Egyptian government has invoked historical claims to the Nile and portrayed Ethiopia's actions as violating international law (Sayed El Ahl, ElTarabishi and Rashad, 2023). This narrative has stoked nationalist anxieties among the Egyptian public, who fear that the GERD could lead to water shortages, economic hardship, and social unrest. The dam symbolises Egypt's vulnerability and serves as a reminder of its historical grievances with Ethiopia (de Souza & Jara, 2023).

Political leaders in both Ethiopia and Egypt have played a crucial role in shaping and amplifying nationalist sentiments surrounding the GERD. They have used the dam to mobilize public support, consolidate their power, and deflect attention from domestic challenges. The rhetoric surrounding the GERD has often been inflammatory, with leaders invoking historical grievances and portraying the other side as an aggressor (Almesafri and Abdo, 2024).

Sudan's position on the GERD reflects a complex interaction of concerns and potential benefits. In Sudan, hydropower generation and water supply are expected to improve under both unilateral and cooperative approaches (Elsayed, H., 2022). Initially fearful about the dam's impact on its water supply, Sudan has started to acknowledge benefits such as flood control and enhanced electricity generation, which could support its development goals (Wedajo, 2024).

However, risks remain during the filling phase, which can reduce water availability and the possibility of increased sedimentation in its dams (Wheeler, K. G., Jeuland, M., Hall, J. W., Zagona, E., & Whittington, D., 2020). It seeks to balance its interests with those of both Ethiopia and Egypt. The international community like the African Union, the United Nations, and various donor countries, plays a vital role in promoting a peaceful resolution to the GERD dispute (Goldberg, 2023). The focus on shared interests, mutual benefits, and long-term sustainability is essential for overcoming the nationalist fervour and reaching a mutually acceptable agreement. However, it has to be noted that nationalism along the

GERD also poses challenges for reaching a cooperative and sustainable solution to the GERD dispute. The heightened nationalist sentiments in both countries make compromise difficult and increase the risk of escalation.

FUNDING THE GRAND ETHIOPIAN RENAISSANCE DAM: A MULTIFACETED APPROACH

Apart from engineering, the GERD also represents a significant financial pooling achievement through domestic resource mobilisation. The estimated construction cost of the dam was \$4.8 billion, which was secured through the employment of diverse strategies (Mahmoud, M. R., 2022). Fund-generating strategies included public contribution, taxation and revenue generation, and state-owned enterprises (Tadese, J., 2022, March 23). The Ethiopian diaspora actively engaged in e-diaspora fundraising efforts that highlighted national pride and commitment to development (Abdulla, M. A., 2024, April 6). The diaspora actively organised events and made substantial donations, reinforcing their connection to Ethiopia's progress (Embassy of Ethiopia, Brussels., 2020, March 25). Additionally, the government issued bonds specifically for the GERD project, both domestically and internationally, and was marketed as patriotic investments and attracted considerable interest from both individuals and institutions (Gevorkyan, A. V., 2021). It proved to be an effective fundraising mechanism. Profits from state-owned enterprises were also channelled towards the dam's construction (Gevorkyan, A. V., 2021). The GERD's funding model serves as an example of how developing countries can leverage their own resources and engage their citizens in national development initiatives. Ethiopia's success in funding demonstrates its commitment to self-reliance and its ability to leverage various financial instruments to achieve its development goals (Wedajo, 2024).

This financial strategy facilitated the GERD's construction and also fostered a sense of unity, despite ongoing regional tensions regarding the dam's operation and filling (Wedajo, 2024). Once operational, the GERD is likely to deliver power to 65 million Ethiopians, supporting the country's development efforts by generating revenue through energy exports to neighbouring countries and serving as a crucial input

for industrialization (Yihdego, 2020). It will also boost industrial growth, agricultural productivity through regulated water flow, and generate revenue from electricity exports to neighbouring countries (Kahsay et al., 2015). **Challenges**

ENVIRONMENTAL AND GEOLOGICAL IMPACTS OF THE GERD

The satellite imagery of the Grand Ethiopian Renaissance Dam (GERD) illustrates the transformation of the Blue Nile between February 2019 and February 2022 (Fig1). In 2019, the river appears as a narrow flow, but by 2022, the GERD reservoir expanded as Ethiopia began filling the dam in stages between 2020 and 2022. The project stands as a symbol of national pride and economic ambition, as it is capable of generating over 5,000 megawatts of power for millions of Ethiopians. For Ethiopia, the GERD embodies the right to utilize its natural resources for national progress without external interference. Hydrologically, the images mark a turning point in the Nile Basin; geopolitically, they reveal shifting power relations—from a century of Egyptian dominance toward a more multipolar basin where upstream countries assert their rights (Beyene, Biederman and Eshete, 2018).

Beyond hydro politics, the reservoir has altered ecosystems, submerged valleys, and reshaped local livelihoods, reminding us that every technological achievement carries ecological and social consequences.

In their study Falco., Giulia and Fiorentino (2022), adopted an ecosystem approach and proposed an analytical model focused on the situation of the GERD on the Blue Nile. According to the study, the GERD is well-suited for applying the ecosystem analytical model. The GERD has far-reaching environmental and geological implications that require careful management and mitigation strategies. Environmental impact assessments have raised concerns about the GERD's downstream effects, on countries like Sudan and Egypt. Study shows that a failure of the GERD can lead to disastrous flooding, threatening infrastructure such as the Roseires, Sennar, and Merowe dams, as well as urban areas like Al Khartoum City and the Aswan High Dam in Egypt (Soliman, M. R., Balah,

A. M., El-Haddad, A., & El-Shorbagy, W., 2018).). The flood risks are worsened by factors such as structural instability and natural disasters, which can result in widespread loss of life and property (Elbelasy, Khater, Hassan & Ibrahim, 2024).

One of the critical environmental challenges posed by the GERD is sediment trapping. Dam captures a significant amount of sediment that would otherwise flow downstream. This can lead to several issues like sediment flushing and dredging. Implementing sediment flushing practices is essential to mitigate sediment accumulation in the reservoir. This involves periodically releasing water through the dam to carry the trapped sediment downstream, thereby reducing the sediment load within the reservoir. Continuous deposition of sediments in the dam would decrease the water-holding capacity of the dam. And it requires regular dredging. Regular dredging can help manage sediment build-up (Seleshi and Scharffenberg, 2020). This process involves removing sediment from the bottom of the reservoir to maintain its capacity and prevent it from becoming overly silted (Abdo, A. L., & Khirelseid, E. M., 2020). However, it has to be noted that, it is an expensive process and countries with a huge number of poverty-stricken can afford this technology.

Plate 1: Satellite imagery of GERD

February 6, 2019 - February 14, 2022

Source: https://eoimages.gsfc.nasa.gov/images/imagerecords/149000/149699/grandeth_oli_201937_lrg.jpg

CHANGE IN MICROCLIMATE:

The accumulation of a large volume of water in the GERD reservoir can significantly alter the region's microclimate. The high rate of evaporation from the reservoir can introduce several climatic changes. High rate of temperatures cause significant water evaporation within tropical countries of horn of Africa, posing a challenge to water management (Mohamed and Elmahdy, 2017). Evaporation losses from the fully developed GERD reservoir are assessed to reach a maximum of 0.4 billion cubic meters (bcm) (Tesfa, 2013). The evaporation of water from the reservoir can increase humidity levels in the surrounding areas. This change in moisture levels can affect local weather patterns, potentially leading to more frequent and intense rainfall. The altered microclimate may result in unpredictable weather events such as cloud bursts and flash floods. The long-term effects of GERD on the Blue Nile's hydrology are also influenced by unpredictable factors like climate change, which can impact future rainfall patterns. These events can pose significant risks to nearby communities, infrastructure, and agriculture (Gebre, S. L., 2020).

The GERD's massive water storage capacity also exerts considerable pressure on the subsurface rock, which can have geological consequences. The weight of the stored water can increase the stress on fault lines and subsurface rock layers. This added pressure can trigger localised earthquakes, known as Reservoir-Induced Seismicity (RIS). These earthquakes are usually minor, and can still pose risks to the dam's structural integrity and the safety of nearby communities (Kaleb, S. E., 2021).

CHANGE IN RIVER FLOW AND HYDROLOGY

GERD has significantly altered the natural flow of river Nile. Blum, Zaitchik, Alexander, Wu, Zhang, Shukla, Alemneh and Block (2019) discovered that Blue Nile's flow was influenced by various factors like rainfall patterns, upstream water use, and evaporation. Predicting the exact increase in summer discharge with perfect accuracy is challenging (Seleshi, Y., & Scharffenberg, W., 2020). The flow of the Blue Nile is expected to be moderate in the long run (Mordos, M. A., Sharfi, E. S. A., Mohammed, B. A., & Wheeler, K., 2020). The GERD's ability to regulate flow could potentially reduce flood peaks by 10-25% and increase average summer discharges by 10-500% depending on the hydrological conditions (Mordos, M. A., Sharfi, E.

S. A., Mohammed, B. A., & Wheeler, K. (2020). In their study, Elkrail and Omer (2015) examined the impact of the GERD's operation on Gezira State, focusing on its effect on groundwater recharge. Gezira State relies heavily on two crucial aquifers: the Nubian and Gezira aquifers, which primarily provide water appropriate for irrigation (Elkrail & Omer, 2015). The scholars concluded that the GERD's ruling of water levels, keeping them consistently high throughout the year, will enhance recharge and increase aquifer seepage. So, this study concludes that there is no adverse impact on aquifers and groundwater.

Fig 1: Water flow from the Blue Nile and Nile River before and after the construction of the GERD

Source: (Tesfa, 2013).

Stagnant water in the reservoir can increase the risk of waterborne diseases such as malaria and schistosomiasis. Adequate health interventions and monitoring are needed to address these risks. Disruptions in water supply can impact access to clean water for drinking and sanitation, with potential public health consequences (Beyene et al., 2018).

The creation of the reservoir is likely to result in habitat loss for terrestrial and aquatic species. This can lead to a reduction in biodiversity and changes in ecosystem dynamics. Alterations in river flow and sediment transport can impact fish populations and fisheries in the Nile, affecting food security and livelihoods for communities that depend on fishing. Changes in water temperature, flow, and quality can adversely affect aquatic ecosystems and biodiversity in the Blue Nile and downstream rivers (Seleshi and Scharffenberg, 2020).

However, the overall environmental impacts remain poorly understood, requiring complete assessments to mitigate risks and prepare emergency response plans (Sharaky, Elewa & Kasem, 2017). Rashad, Shaaban and Mago (2022), highlight the importance of assessing the dam's stability and potential failure scenarios, emphasizing the need for emergency action plans to mitigate extreme disasters like floods that could affect downstream countries.

OPPORTUNITIES EGYPT'S AGRICULTURE: ADAPTATION IN THE FACE OF WATER SCARCITY

The GERD poses a significant impact on Egypt's agricultural sector. It has been seen that Egypt's agricultural practices are evolving in response to the GERD and a series of transformative and adaptive measures to ensure food security and economic stability (Kandeel, A., 2021). According to Peng, Li, He, Cai, Zhang, Belete, Deng and Wang, (2022), Ethiopia's construction of the dam has led to challenges for Egypt's water and food security, escalating economic burdens. In response to anticipated water scarcity, Egypt is applying adaptive strategies, i.e. from crop selection, modern drip, and precision irrigation techniques to policy reforms and technological innovations (Peng et al., 2022). There is a shift towards drought-resistant crop varieties and crop diversification aims to reduce reliance on water-intensive crops like rice, which is known for its high-water consumption (Peng et al., 2022). In order to improve water efficiency in the cultivation of rice, modern irrigation techniques including alternating wetting and drying (AWD) are being used. These techniques considerably reduce water usage while maintaining yields (Lampayan, R.M., et.al. 2015). Furthermore, the nation is spending money on reusing treated wastewater for irrigation, especially for non-food crops, as this has been shown to be more cost-effective than using conventional groundwater sources (Wahid, Khairy & Krause, 2024). Moreover, investigating unconventional water sources like air conditioner condensate and rainfall offers more chances for sustainable irrigation. Taken together, these actions show a thorough strategy for managing water resources in the face of increasing scarcity (Gnedy, Daoud and Elmansy, 2023). Collectively, these measures replicate a wide-ranging approach to managing water resources amidst rising shortage. Elevated low flows from the GERD are likely to improve the water-food-energy nexus outcomes in Egypt under a complete assistance governance scenario, with a slight decrease in GERD hydropower

generation of 2,000 GWh/year (19%) (Elsayed et al., 2022).

NEGOTIATION AND DIPLOMACY

INTERNATIONAL AND REGIONAL GOVERNANCE

The dialogues surrounding the GERD have become a focal point for international and regional governance efforts, particularly involving the World Bank (WB), UN, UN Security Council (UNSC), and AU (De Falco & Fiorentino, 2022). The UN emphasized promoting international water law concepts that support fair water-sharing agreements among Nile Basin countries for conflict prevention and peaceful settlement (De Falco, S. and Fiorentino, G., 2022). It also aims to address the needs of vulnerable populations affected by water management strategies. Conversely, the WB offers vital financial capital and technical know-how for cooperative water management projects, facilitating dialogue among Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt concerning the GERD (De Souza *et al.*, 2023). However, the success of these struggles is hampered by historical treaties that favour downstream states and an absence of robust implementation mechanisms within the Nile Basin Initiative (NBI) (Wouters and De Chazournes, 2018). Regardless of these challenges, improving the NBI's capacity might foster cooperation and lessen conflicts, emphasizing the necessity for integrative negotiation approaches to resolve ongoing disputes (Wedajo, 2024).

ROLE OF THE AFRICAN UNION:

AU plays a pivotal in mediating the GERD disputes by promoting the principle of “African solutions for African problems” to foster regional ownership (Tawfik, 2023). The creation of the International Panel of Experts and the Declaration of Principles show that, despite the lack of a legally enforceable agreement, AU-led negotiations have reduced the likelihood of future escalations (Wedajo, 2024). The AU's formal involvement began in **mid-2020** and matter was elevated to the **highest organs of the Union** including the **Assembly of Heads of State and Government** and the **Bureau of the Assembly**. This top-level engagement was not merely procedural but it shows **strong political commitments**. The AU became the platform through which Africa find an African solution to an African challenge. **Peace and Security Council did not take** direct control of the technical negotiations. But it offered a vital **institutional**

framework for dialogue and de-escalation. It reminded all parties that the dispute over the Nile was not just about water, but also about **regional peace and collective security** (Tawfik, M., 2023).

In order to address security issues related to water shortages and climate change in the future and work toward a lasting resolution in the region, the AU's sustained involvement is crucial (Birhan, 2024). After tensions escalated between Ethiopia, Sudan, and Egypt over the GERD, the AU stepped in as a mediator in 2020. African Union (AU) has been approached to mediate the dispute, providing an opportunity to leverage its continental peace architecture framework through three main avenues: the Assembly of Heads of State and Government, which is the AU's supreme policy and decision-making body; the AU Peace and Security Council (APSC), the cornerstone of the AU's conflict prevention, management, and resolution framework; and the involvement of COMESA, the largest Regional Economic Community of the AU, aimed at promoting regional integration through trade and the development of natural and human resources (Tawfik, M., 2023). South Africa's president, acting as the AU Chair at the time, played a key role in facilitating negotiations (Tawfik, M., 2023). The AU's involvement helped to de-escalate tensions and prevent the dispute from reaching a boiling point (Tawfik, M., 2023). This encourages regional ownership of the issue and avoids external interference (Kasimbazi & Bamwine, 2021).

Despite these efforts, the AU hasn't yet been able to broker a concluding agreement on the GERD filling and operation process. Technical and legal issues remain sticking points. The AU lacks strong enforcement mechanisms to compel countries to adhere to agreements. Success relies on the willingness of all parties to negotiate in good faith. The AU faces the challenge of balancing the interests of all Nile Basin countries, which have varying needs and historical claims to the Nile water (Teshale, S. and Abebe, F., 2022).

THE UNITED STATES AND CHINA'S POSITIONS ON THE GRAND ETHIOPIAN RENAISSANCE DAM: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

GERD has attracted attention from global powers like the United States and China, who have contrasting approaches to the issue. The U.S. advocates for a multilateral, mediated solution, while China takes a more hands-off approach, focusing on bilateral relations with the involved countries. Significant steps

in the GERD negotiations include the formation of the International Panel of Experts, the Declaration of Principles, and the establishment of a Joint Research Group, with the U.S. and World Bank serving as observers (Khorrami, N., 2021). Despite these efforts, unresolved issues such as drought mitigation, a binding agreement, dam safety, and dispute resolution remain. These global powers' involvement adds another layer to an already intricate negotiation landscape (Tamerat, Y. and Haile, B., 2023).

THE UNITED STATES' POSITION:

The U.S.' active involvement and pressure tactics have made it a significant player in the GERD negotiations. The location of the dam was recognized and suggested in a study done by the US Bureau of Reclamation during a study of the Blue Nile amid 1956 and 1964 (Beyene, M. Z., Biederman, J. and Eshete, K., 2018). The Bureau deliberated for the dam to produce 1,400 MW of power with a reservoir volume of 11 billion cubic meters (bcm) (Ahmed & Elsanabary, 2015). It advocates for a multilateral, mediated solution that addresses the concerns of all riparian countries.

The U.S. has a vested interest in regional stability and conflict prevention in the Nile Basin. It also seeks to promote its values of transparency, rule of law, and equitable resource sharing. The U.S. has engaged in diplomatic efforts at various levels, including high-level visits, technical assistance, and financial support for mediation efforts (Solomon, B., 2020). It has also exerted pressure on Ethiopia to reach an agreement, including withholding aid and imposing sanctions. While it has expressed interest in a peaceful resolution, its actions haven't translated into a comprehensive political strategy. However, its recent actions have also drawn criticism from Ethiopia, which perceives them as interference in its internal affairs. The U.S. has expressed support for the African Union-led negotiations and has urged the parties to reach a comprehensive and legally binding agreement (Kifle, Z., 2024).

CHINA'S POSITION:

China has played a significant role in the GERD in Ethiopia, primarily through financing and construction. They've provided loans exceeding \$1 billion and are estimated to be involved in related power transmission projects (China AidData, 2023). China's involvement can be seen as part of its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), aiming to develop infrastructure

projects globally and expand its economic influence. China has also supplied construction materials and technology for the dam (Oduro, G. B., 2022). Chinese companies, like Sinohydro and Gezhouba Group, have been awarded major construction contracts for the GERD (Zola, A., 2023). This brings Chinese engineering expertise to the project (Klaassen, 2021). China's primary interest in the region is economic. It has significant investments in infrastructure projects in all three countries and seeks to maintain good relations with all parties. China has encouraged the parties to resolve their differences through dialogue and consultation.

While China's direct influence on the GERD negotiations is limited, its economic clout and close ties with the involved countries give it potential leverage. China generally maintains a policy of non-interference in other countries' internal affairs. In other words, we can say that China has adopted a more hands-off approach to the GERD, emphasizing its bilateral relations with the involved countries. It has refrained from taking a strong public stance on the issue (Verhoeven, H., 2021). However, supporting the GERD aligns with their goal of promoting African development and infrastructure projects. China maintains diplomatic relations with both Ethiopia and Egypt.

While supporting the GERD, they have also encouraged dialogue and a peaceful resolution to the water-sharing dispute. China's involvement in the GERD project has shifted the supremacy undercurrents in the Nile Basin. It challenges Egypt's historical dominance over Nile water and offers Ethiopia more leverage in negotiations. Egypt has expressed concerns about the potential impact of the GERD on its water flow and security. This has created some tension between Egypt and China (Verhoeven, H., 2021).

The United States and China's differing positions on the GERD reflect their distinct interests and approaches to international relations. The U.S.'s active involvement and pressure tactics contrast with China's more hands-off, bilateral approach (Khorrami, N., 2021).

The future trajectory of the GERD negotiations and the broader implications for regional stability will likely be influenced by the evolving positions of these two global powers. A cooperative approach between the U.S. and China, focusing on shared interests and mutual respect for the sovereignty of the involved countries,

could potentially facilitate a peaceful and sustainable resolution to the GERD dispute. However, continued divergence in their approaches could complicate the negotiations and exacerbate existing tensions in the Nile Basin(Khorrami, N., 2021).

To mitigate the tension, a benefit-sharing approach has been proposed. This approach aims to sustain the Nile ecosystem, promote regional peace, increase water flow, and decrease unnecessary expenses through modest intraregional cooperation. The resolution of the Nile Basin conflict relies on identifying the potential of the basin and adopting integrated cooperative frameworks. Such frameworks should be developed by the technocrats of riparian states and international experts to manage the shared water resources effectively (Hailu, A.S., 2022).

CONCLUSION

Managing transboundary rivers like the Nile is difficult, especially with weak or non-existent river basin institutions. To ensure the GERD benefits all riparian countries and supports regional prosperity, it is essential to prioritize equitable water-sharing, transparent communication, and regional collaboration. Ongoing negotiations should focus on a cooperative approach that includes joint infrastructure projects, knowledge sharing, and drought preparedness rather than just addressing the GERD. The negotiations should aim for a comprehensive framework for sustainable Nile water management, considering climate change and population growth. The GERD dispute, if resolved successfully, could become a model for future transboundary water cooperation in the Nile Basin and beyond.

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